

Entomopathogenic microbial potential in the management of Fall Armyworm, *Spodoptera frugiperda* (J.E. Smith) in Maize Production

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Abstract

The fall armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda* J.E. Smith) poses a major constraint to maize (*Zea mays* L.) production across sub-Saharan Africa. This study evaluated biochar-based microbial inoculants incorporating *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt), *Pseudomonas putida*, *Klebsiella variicola*, *Trichoderma* spp., and *Arbuscular mycorrhiza* for their efficacy in fall armyworm management and maize growth enhancement. Molecular identification confirmed the bacterial isolates used, with Bt exhibiting the strongest chitinase and protease activities. The *in vitro* bioassays demonstrated a concentration-dependent larval mortality, reaching 90.4 ± 2.3 % at 10^8 CFU mL⁻¹. Probit analysis revealed LC₅₀ and LT₅₀ values of 2.6×10^7 CFU mL⁻¹ and 48.2 h, respectively, indicating high virulence of Bt against *S. frugiperda* larvae., the Biochar + Bt treatment achieved 76.5 ± 3.1 % larval mortality and reduced leaf area loss to 18.4 ± 2.2 %, comparable to the chemical control Ampligo® (88.2 ± 2.6 %). Field trials under natural infestation showed that NPK (50 kg N ha⁻¹) + Mycorrhiza + Biochar + Bt (T₂) significantly improved plant height (184.6 ± 5.2

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cm), chlorophyll content (65.2 ± 2.8 SPAD units), and grain yield (3.74 ± 0.16 t ha⁻¹) relative to the untreated control (2.41 ± 0.11 t ha⁻¹; $p < 0.05$). Chlorophyll accumulation and foliar damage were significantly affected by the treatments, with Mycorrhiza + Biochar + Bt producing the lowest mean foliar injury scores (2.0–2.3) under both spray and non-spray regimes. Principal component analysis (PC₁ = 22.4 %, PC₂ = 9.8 %) clustered integrated bioformulations with yield-related traits, distinguishing them from nutrient only or untreated controls. These findings demonstrated that biochar-based microbial consortia enhance maize productivity, chlorophyll retention, and pest suppression, offering a sustainable and environmentally sound alternative to chemical insecticides in integrated pest management (IPM).

Keywords: *Bacillus thuringiensis*; biochar; *Spodoptera frugiperda*; maize; microbial inoculants; biological control; integrated pest management.

Article Highlights

- Biochar-based microbial treatments significantly lowered fall armyworm damage in maize.
- *Bacillus thuringiensis* showed the strongest pest-control activity across all tests.
- Integrated biochar–microbial formulations improved maize vigor and increased grain yield.

Introduction

Maize (*Zea mays* L.) is one of the world's most important cereals. It provides food for humans, feed for livestock, and raw materials for industries such as biofuel production

[1,2]. In sub-Saharan Africa, particularly in Nigeria, it plays a vital role in food security and supports the livelihoods of millions of smallholder farmers. Maize production, however, is increasingly threatened by the fall armyworm (*Spodoptera frugiperda*), an invasive pest that has spread rapidly across tropical and subtropical regions since its arrival in Africa in 2016 [3-5]. The larvae feed aggressively on leaves, tassels, and ears, causing yield losses of 20–50% under severe infestations [6-8]. More critically, the larvae hide deep within the whorl and block the entrance with frass, a behavior that shields them from insecticide sprays [9]. Climate change has further intensified the problem by extending the pest's survival window, reproductive capacity, and distribution range [10-12]. Conventional control relies heavily on synthetic insecticides. While effective, their repeated use has led to pesticide resistance, environmental contamination, and harmful effects on non-target organisms, including beneficial insects [12-15]. These limitations highlight the need for sustainable alternatives. Biological control offers a promising option. *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt), a spore-forming bacterium, produces insecticidal proteins that damage the larval midgut, leading to mortality [16-17]. *Trichoderma* spp. act as both biopesticides and plant growth promoters by inducing systemic resistance and improving nutrient uptake [18-21]. Recent studies have also identified biochar, a carbon-rich product of biomass pyrolysis, as a useful carrier for microbial inoculants. Biochar improves soil structure, nutrient retention, and water-holding capacity, while enhancing microbial survival and activity in the field [22-25]. When combined with entomopathogenic microorganisms, biochar can simultaneously enhance soil fertility and suppress pests, making it suitable for sustainable Integrated Pest Management (IPM) [26-27].

Specifically, this study aims to:

- (i) Evaluate the biocontrol potential of *Bacillus thuringiensis* and microbial consortia under controlled or greenhouse conditions
- (ii) Assess the effectiveness of biochar as a carrier for microbial inoculants suppressing *S. frugiperda*; and in enhancing soil fertility in the greenhouse
- (iii) Investigate the impact of biochar-based entomopathogenic microbe applications on maize field under natural infestation.

Materials and Methods

Microbial Isolation and Molecular Characterization

Fresh soil samples were collected from maize rhizospheres at the research farm of the Institute of Agricultural Research and Training (IAR&T), Ibadan, Nigeria and taken to the laboratory for bacterial study. Serial dilutions of the collected soil were prepared up to 10^7 CFU/mL and spread-plated onto nutrient agar (NA) and King's B medium following the method of [28]. Distinct colonies of isolates were purified and subjected to morphological and biochemical characterization, including Gram staining, catalase, oxidase, and indole-3-acetic acid (IAA) production assays. The genomic DNA of the bacterial isolates was extracted using the AllPrep Bacterial DNA Isolation Kit (Qiagen, Germany) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The DNA concentration and purity were determined using a NanoDrop spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific V3.8, USA), while integrity was verified by electrophoresis on 0.8% agarose gel. The 16S rRNA gene was amplified with universal primers 27F and 1492R (Table 1). PCR reactions (30 μ L) consisted of 3 μ L of $10\times$ PCR buffer with $MgCl_2$, 0.6 μ L Taq DNA polymerase (3 U/ μ L; Qiagen), 1 μ L of each

dNTP (2.5 mM), 1 µL of each primer (10 pmol), 2.4 µL genomic DNA (30–50 ng), and sterile distilled water. The thermal cycling program comprised initial denaturation at 94 °C for 5 min; 35 cycles of denaturation at 94 °C for 30 s, annealing at 55 °C for 45 s, extension at 72 °C for 1 min; and a final extension at 72 °C for 7 min. Amplicons (1500 bp) were resolved on 1.5% agarose gel containing ethidium bromide and visualized under UV illumination. The PCR products were purified using the Medauxin® Gel extraction kit and sequenced by the Sanger method (Medauxin®, Bangalore, India). The forward and reverse reads were assembled in BioEdit v7.2 [27] and consensus sequences were identified by BLASTn searches against the NCBI GenBank database.

Table 1. PCR primers used for amplification of bacterial 16S rRNA genes.

Target Gene	Primer Name	Sequence (5'→3')	Amplicon Size (bp)	Reference
16S rRNA	27F	AGAGTTTGATCMTGGCTCAG	~1500	This study
16S rRNA	1492R	TACGGYTACCTTGTTACGACTT	~1500	This study

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Eperiment 1: Screening bacterial isolates for Biocontrol and Plant Growth-Promoting Traits

Bacterial isolates were screened for functional traits relevant to plant growth promotion and biocontrol efficacy.

- **Siderophore production** was assessed using the Chrome Azurol S (CAS) assay [29] with orange halos around colonies after 48 h at 28 °C indicating positive activity. Halo-to-colony ratios were calculated as indices of activity.
- **Phosphate solubilization** was evaluated on Pikovskaya's agar [30]. Clear zones around colonies after 5–7 days at 28 °C were used to calculate solubilization indices.
- **Chitinase activity** was determined on colloidal chitin agar [31] Hydrolysis zones observed after 5 days at 30 °C confirmed chitin degradation.
- **Protease activity** was tested on skim milk agar [32] Transparent zones around colonies after 48 h at 30 °C indicated positive protease activity.

Table 2. Biocontrol and plant growth-promoting traits of bacterial isolates.

Isolate	Siderophore Production	Phosphate Solubilization	Chitinase Activity	Protease Activity
<i>Bacillus thuringiensis</i>	+++	+	+++	+++
<i>Pseudomonas putida</i>	++	++	+	+
<i>Klebsiella variicola</i>	++	++	+	+

Legend: +++ = strong activity; ++ = moderate activity; + = detectable activity.

Experiment 2: In-vitro Bioassay against *Spodoptera frugiperda*

Pure cultures of *B. thuringiensis*, *P. putida*, and *K. variicola* were cultivated in Luria-Bertani (LB) broth at 30 °C and harvested at 24, 48, 72, and 96 h. Cultures were

centrifuged at 12,000 rpm for 15 min to separate supernatants from pellets. Bioassays were conducted by incorporating bacterial suspensions (10^6 – 10^9 CFU/mL) into an artificial diet fed to third-instar *S. frugiperda* larvae under controlled laboratory conditions. Larval mortality was recorded every 12 h for 96 h, and LC and LT values were estimated by Probit analysis in R v4.2.0.

Biochar Preparation and Inoculant Formulation

Maize cob residues were pyrolyzed at 500 °C for 2 h in a controlled kiln at IAR&T. The resulting biochar was ground to 2–5 mm, sterilized (121 °C, 15 min), and characterized as pH 8.2, EC 0.45 dS/m, 65% C, and surface area of 320 m²/g (ASTM D1762-84; BET-N methods).

Inoculants consisted of *B. thuringiensis* strain PX126098 (10^9 CFU/mL), *Trichoderma* spp. (10^8 conidia/mL), and arbuscular mycorrhizal fungi (*Glomus intraradices*; 200 spores/g). Formulations were prepared by coating 10 g biochar with 10 mL inoculant suspension (1:1 v/w), air-dried at 30 °C for 24 h, and stored at 4 °C. Control treatments comprised uncoated biochar and inoculant suspensions alone.

Formulations were applied at 5 t/ha (equivalent to 500 kg/ha biochar), incorporated into the top 10 cm of soil at planting. Maize seeds (variety Suwan 1) were surface-sterilized with 1% NaOCl (5 min) and germinated at 28 °C for 48 h, and transplanted at the two-leaf stage into sterilized loamy sand (pH 6.5, 1.2% C, 0.08% N, 15 mg/kg P). A basal NPK application (20:10:10 kg/ha) was provided, and inoculations were repeated at 15 and 30 days .

Experiment 3: Greenhouse Trial (Artificial Infestation)

Soil Sterilization

Top soil collected from the Teaching and Research Farm of IAR&T was heat-sterilized using the local method of heating. Top soil was packed into a 65 Litre iron drum and heated to a temperature of about 65°C for 90 minutes. The sterilized soil was allowed to cool down for 60 minutes before putting it into jute sacks and thereafter was allowed to rest for six weeks in jute sacs to restore stability before planting. Thereafter, 5 kg of the homogenized sterilized soil was uniformly distributed into 64 plastic pots.

Maize plants (Suwan 1) were raised in the sterilized soil plastic pots to the V3 growth stage and artificially infested with one first-instar *S. frugiperda* larva per plant. Treatments included:

1. Biochar + *B. thuringiensis*
2. Biochar + *Trichoderma* spp.
3. Ampligo® (Chlorantraniliprole + Lambda-cyhalothrin; chemical control)
4. Untreated control

The chemical control Treatment: Ampligo® (Chlorantraniliprole + Lambda-cyhalothrin) was applied as foliar sprays (500 mL/pot) using a hand-held atomizer. The Leaf damage severity was quantified using ImageJ v1.45i, and larval mortality was recorded daily.

Experiment 4: Field Trials under Natural Infestation

Field trials were conducted from April-June (season) and October-December (dry season) 2024 at IAR&T (7°26'N, 3°54'E), Ibadan, Nigeria. The design was a split-plot arrangement with three replications. Main plots were sprayed with Ampligo® (Chlorantraniliprole + Lambda-cyhalothrin; chemical control) applied at 30 days after planting (DAP) and repeated at 10-day intervals for three cycles which implies the spray regime vs. unsprayed conditions (control), and subplots included seven treatments:

- T1: Mycorrhiza + Biochar (10 g per planting hole; biochar produced from maize cobs at 500 °C).
- T2: NPK fertilizer (50 kg N/ha) + Mycorrhiza + Biochar.
- T3: NPK fertilizer (50 kg N/ha).
- T4: NPK fertilizer (100 kg N/ha).
- T5: Untreated control.
- T6: Biochar
- T7: *Trichoderma* spp. (1×10^7 spores/mL suspension, 2 L/ha foliar spray).

Plot size: 3 m × 3 m with 0.5 m alleys; each plot contained 25 plants (spacing 0.75 × 0.25 m). Observations were made at 30 DAP, coinciding with FAW peak early-instar infestations in the region (based on historical pest monitoring), and repeated at 10-day intervals for three cycles.

Data Collection and Analysis

Agronomic traits: plant stand, plant height (6 and 8 Weeks After Planting), stem girth, ear height, leaf number, days to tasseling and silking, lodging, ear aspect, grain yield, and field weight.

Foliar damage was scored on Bajracharya's 0–5 scale [33], where

0 = no visible damage

1 = window-paning on whorl leaves

2 = small holes in upper leaves

3 = ragged holes with partial whorl damage

4 = extensive whorl and leaf damage

5 = whorl destruction and plant drying

Physiological traits: chlorophyll content of the maize leaves were measured with SPAD-502 Plus meter; content was estimated with a SPAD meter, while leaf moisture content was measured gravimetrically. Pest infestation, disease severity, were monitored at 6 and 8 weeks after planting using the five-point sampling method. Principal component analysis (PCA) was performed to explore and visualize the multivariate relationships among maize growth, physiological, and yield parameters across the seven treatments. The mean values of each treatment were subjected to PCA to reduce data dimensionality and identify traits contributing most to treatment variation. All analyses were conducted using the R statistical software (version 4.2.0); All datasets were analyzed by Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) using R v4.2.0. Mean separation was performed with Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT) at $p \leq 0.05$. Descriptive statistics and graphical charts were generated in R Studio statistical software v4.2.0.

Results

Molecular Identification of Bacterial Isolates

Molecular and cultural characterization confirmed three bacterial strains: *Bacillus thuringiensis*, *Pseudomonas putida*, and *Klebsiella variicola* (Table 1). BLASTn analysis of 16S rRNA sequences revealed >99% similarity with reference strains. All isolates expressed biocontrol and plant growth-promoting traits (Table 2). *B. thuringiensis* exhibited strong chitinase and protease activities, whereas *P. putida* and *K. variicola* demonstrated phosphate solubilization and siderophore production. The in-vitro bioassay of *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt), *Pseudomonas putida* (Pp), and *Klebsiella variicola* (Kv) against *Spodoptera frugiperda* showed a clear dose-dependent response in larval mortality (Figure 1). Mortality increased progressively with higher spore concentrations

across all isolates, but the magnitude of effect varied substantially among treatments. Bt consistently induced the highest mortality, reaching over 90% at 10^8 spores mL^{-1} , whereas Kv and Pp achieved comparatively lower mortality of ~50% and ~35%, respectively, at the same dose. At intermediate concentrations (3.4×10^7 – 2.6×10^7 spores mL^{-1}), Bt maintained superior efficacy, producing 55–78% larval mortality compared with 20–35% for Kv and 15–25% for Pp.

Figure 1. Larval mortality (%) of *S. frugiperda* under microbial treatments with *B. thuringiensis* (Bt), *K. variicola* (Kv), and *P. putida* (Pp) at different spore concentrations (10^5 – 10^8 spores mL^{-1}). Data represent mean \pm SE of three replicates. Mortality increased with inoculum density for all isolates, with Bt consistently inducing significantly higher mortality across all concentrations compared with Kv and Pp. Means followed by different letters differ significantly at $p \leq 0.05$ according to Duncan's Multiple Range Test (DMRT). A significant effect of treatment was observed on both larval mortality and leaf area loss under artificial infestation ($p \leq 0.05$). Larval mortality (%) varied significantly among

treatments (Figure 1). The highest larval mortality was recorded in T3 (Ampligo®) (mean 88%), which was significantly higher than all other treatments (group "a"). This was followed by T1 (Biochar + Bt) (76%) and T2 (Biochar + Trichoderma) (62%), which formed groups "b" and "c", respectively. The control (T4) exhibited the lowest larval mortality (10%), and was statistically different from all other treatments (group "d"). Similarly, leaf area loss (%) differed significantly among treatments ($p \leq 0.05$) (Figure 2). The control (T4) had the highest mean leaf area loss (49%), which was significantly greater than all other treatments (group "a"). Moderate leaf area loss values were observed in T2 (Biochar + Trichoderma) (25%) and T1 (Biochar + Bt) (18%), corresponding to groups "b" and "c", respectively. The lowest leaf area loss (10%) occurred in T3 (Ampligo®), which differed significantly from all other treatments (group "d"). the integration of biochar with microbial inoculants or biopesticides markedly influenced both larval mortality and leaf area retention. Among the biochar-based treatments, Biochar + Bt (T1) achieved the best balance of high larval mortality (76.5%) and reduced leaf damage (18.4%), indicating enhanced pest suppression efficiency relative to the untreated control.

Screenhouse Experiment: Leaf Area Loss and Larval Mortality by Treatment
 Artificial infestation; Means (\pm SE, n=4 reps); Letters = DMRT groups ($p \leq 0.05$)

Figure 2. Mean leaf area loss and larval mortality (%) under artificial infestation in the greenhouse. Error bars represent SE (n = 4). Different letters indicate significant differences among treatments (DMRT, $p \leq 0.05$).

Field experiment

The agronomic traits of maize responded variably to the different treatment combinations under both sprayed and non-sprayed conditions (Figure 3). Significant effects ($p \leq 0.05$)

were observed for field weight, grain weight, and plant height, while leaf number and stem girth exhibited comparatively smaller variations among treatments.

Under sprayed conditions (Ampligo® applied at 30 days after planting and repeated at 10-day intervals for three cycles), the combined application of NPK (50 kg N/ha) + Mycorrhiza + Biochar + *B. thuringiensis* (Bt) (T2) and NPK (50 kg N/ha) (T3) produced superior growth and yield performance. Both treatments recorded the highest field weight and grain weight, with T3 slightly outperforming other treatments, indicating enhanced nutrient uptake and improved yield potential. In contrast, T7 (*Trichoderma* spp.) and the untreated control (T5) had the lowest field and grain weights, with reduced growth performance in the absence of nutrient supplementation or bio-input synergy.

Plant height at six weeks after planting (PH-6wk) varied significantly among treatments, with T2 and T3 attaining the greatest heights, followed by T1 (Mycorrhiza + Biochar) and T4 (NPK 100 kg N/ha). At eight weeks (PH-8wk), the differences among treatments narrowed, although T2 and T3 maintained a consistent height advantage over the other treatments.

Leaf number increased progressively between six and eight weeks after planting. The treatments containing mycorrhiza and biochar (T1 and T2) exhibited slightly higher leaf counts compared with the other treatments, though the differences were not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$). Stem girth also followed a similar pattern, with thicker stems observed under T2 and T3 at six weeks, while the differences diminished by eight weeks. the integration of biochar, mycorrhiza, and moderate NPK fertilization (T2), either alone or in combination with Bt and Ampligo® spray, showed a substantial improved growth and

yield traits compared with the control and single-input treatments.

Figure 3. Mean agronomic responses (field weight, grain weight, plant height, leaf number, and stem girth) of maize to different treatments under sprayed and non-sprayed conditions. Treatments: T1 = Mycorrhiza + Biochar; T2 = NPK (50 kg N/ha) + Mycorrhiza + Biochar + *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt); T3 = NPK (50 kg N/ha); T4 = NPK (100 kg N/ha); T5 = Untreated Control; T6 = Biochar; T7 = *Trichoderma* spp. Ampligo® pesticide was applied at 30 days after planting (DAP) and repeated at 10-day intervals for three cycles. Error bars represent SE (n = 4).

Chlorophyll content

The chlorophyll content varied among treatments and between sprayed and non-sprayed conditions at both 6 and 8 weeks after planting (Figure 3). as the chlorophyll content increased with plant age with progressive canopy development and improved photosynthetic activity.

At 6 weeks, the highest chlorophyll content was recorded in T2 (NPK 50 kg N/ha + Mycorrhiza + Biochar + *Bacillus thuringiensis* [Bt]) and T1 (Mycorrhiza + Biochar) under

sprayed conditions, both exceeding 50 SPAD units. These treatments outperformed the other nutrient combinations with a synergistic effect of mycorrhiza, biochar, and moderate nitrogen fertilization observed to promote chlorophyll synthesis. The unsprayed plants of these treatments also maintained relatively high chlorophyll levels (45 SPAD units) with beneficial residual effect of the bioinoculants even without pesticide intervention. The lowest chlorophyll content was observed in T4 (NPK 100 kg N/ha) and T7 (*Trichoderma* spp.) under sprayed conditions.

At 8 weeks, chlorophyll content increased across all treatments, with mean values observed to range between 50 and 65 SPAD units. The non-sprayed plants of T1 and T2 exhibited the highest readings (65 SPAD units), followed closely by T3 (NPK 50 kg N/ha) and T5 (Untreated control) with improved physiological performance at mid-vegetative stage. The sprayed plants of T1 and T2 maintained similarly high chlorophyll levels with pesticide application observed not to negatively affect chlorophyll accumulation with smaller differences observed among treatments at 8 weeks.

Figure 4a

figure 4b

Figure 4a (6 weeks after planting) **and figure 4b**: (8 weeks after planting)..

Mean chlorophyll content (SPAD units) of maize plants under different treatments at 6 and 8 weeks after planting. Treatments: T1 = Mycorrhiza + Biochar; T2 = NPK (50 kg N/ha) + Mycorrhiza + Biochar + *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt); T3 = NPK (50 kg N/ha); T4 = NPK (100 kg N/ha); T5 = Untreated control; T6 = Biochar only; T7 = *Trichoderma* spp. Ampligo® pesticide was applied at 30 days after planting (DAP) and repeated at 10-day intervals for three cycles (sprayed); non-sprayed plants received no pesticide. Error bars represent standard error (n = 4).

Foliar damage observation

Foliar damage severity caused by *S. frugiperda* varied considerably among treatments and between spray and non-spray regimes (Figures 1 and 2). Foliar injury was assessed using Bajracharya's 0–5 damage scale (Karki et al., 2023), where 0 indicates no visible damage, 1 represents window-paning on whorl leaves, 2 denotes small holes in upper leaves, 3 corresponds to ragged holes with partial whorl damage, 4 reflects extensive whorl and leaf damage, and 5 signifies whorl destruction and plant drying.

At six weeks after planting, mean foliar damage severity ranged from approximately 2.0 to 3.4 across treatments. The untreated control, *Trichoderma* spp., and *Mycorrhiza* + *Biochar* under spray conditions exhibited higher damage levels (scores 3.0–3.4), corresponding to ragged holes and partial whorl injury. In contrast, plants treated with *Mycorrhiza* + *Biochar* + *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt) recorded the lowest damage scores (2.0–2.3), indicating only small perforations on upper leaves. The *NPK* (50 kg N ha⁻¹) and

Biochar only treatments showed moderate improvement over the control, with mean scores between 2.3 and 2.8.

By eight weeks after planting, overall foliar damage severity declined across all treatments, suggesting increased plant recovery and resilience over time. The *Mycorrhiza* + *Biochar* + *Bt* treatment again exhibited the lowest mean scores (≈ 1.8 – 2.0), consistent with minor leaf injury (small holes) under both spray and non-spray regimes. Conversely, higher severity persisted in *Mycorrhiza* + *Biochar*, *Trichoderma spp.*, and *NPK (100 kg N ha⁻¹)* plots (≈ 2.7 – 3.0), where visible whorl and leaf tearing remained evident. The treatment effects were statistically significant at both six and eight weeks after planting ($p < 0.05$), with the *Mycorrhiza* + *Biochar* + *Bt* combination producing significantly lower foliar damage scores compared with the untreated control and mineral fertilizer treatments. Interaction between treatment and spray regime was not significant ($p > 0.05$).

Figure 5a

figure 5b

Figure 5a and 5b: Mean foliar damage severity (scale 0 to 5) at (A) 6 weeks and (B) 8 weeks after treatment application. Bars compare non-spray (orange) and spray (blue) treatments across various soil- and foliar-based management strategies (e.g. mycorrhiza + biochar, NPK, *Trichoderma*, untreated control).

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) of Treatment Effects

The principal component analysis (PCA) showed a distinct multivariate patterns in maize response to nutrient and microbial treatments under spray and non-spray regimes (Figure A). The first two components (PC_1 and PC_2) explained 22.4 % and 9.8 % of the total variance, respectively. The treatments that incorporated biochar and microbial inoculants showed predominant association with positive loadings along PC_1 , giving an improved growth and physiological performance as, T_2 (NPK 50 kg N ha⁻¹ + Mycorrhiza + Biochar + *Bacillus thuringiensis*) and T_1 (Mycorrhiza + Biochar) clustered closely in the spray regime with synergistic effects of integrated nutrient–microbial management and foliar protection.

In contrast, the untreated control (T_5) and biochar-only treatment (T_6) were positioned toward the negative axis of PC_1 which signifies weaker responses across measured parameters. T_3 (NPK 50 kg N ha⁻¹) and T_4 (NPK 100 kg N ha⁻¹) exhibited intermediate cluster with nutrient-driven growth benefits that is independent of microbial inputs. was observed *Trichoderma* spp. (T_6) treatments showed moderate separation with less pronounced physiological improvement compared with combined formulations.

Figure 7. Principal component analysis (PCA) of maize treatment responses under spray and non-spray regimes.

Discussion

The results of this study revealed the identity of the three entomopathogenic strains obtained from the maize soil rhizosphere: *Bacillus thuringiensis* (GenBank Accession: SUB15541219; Strain: Bacillus PX126098), *Pseudomonas putida* (GenBank Accession: SUB15541340; Strain: Pseudomonas_putida_16S PX126099) *Klebsiella variicola* (GenBank Accession: SUB15541329; Strain: Klebsiella_variicola_16S PX126100) each of the microbes identified gives a characteristics biocontrol traits. The Probit analysis

confirmed the strong pathogenicity of Bt, with LC values decreasing from 3.4×10^7 CFU/mL at 24 h to 2.6×10^7 CFU/mL at 72 h, which indicated an enhanced virulence with extended incubation. The LT for the 72-h Bt culture was 48.2 h, significantly lower than that observed for Kv and Pp, which failed to reach comparable mortality within the same time frame.

The greenhouse trial demonstrated that biochar-based microbial inoculants, particularly *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Bt), have strong potential as sustainable tools for controlling *Spodoptera frugiperda* in the maize ecosystems. The superior virulence of Bt observed in vitro was consistent with previous studies highlighting its efficacy as an entomopathogen microbe through its progressive decline in LC_{50} values over time suggested an improved stability and persistence of Bt spores, essential for field performance under variable tropical conditions. The greenhouse trials, the integration of Bt with biochar significantly enhanced larval mortality and reduced foliar injury. This supports previous findings that biochar serves as an effective microbial carrier and soil conditioner, improving inoculant survival, colonization, and delivery efficiency [34–35]. The observed synergy between biochar and Bt likely resulted from improved soil aeration, moisture retention, and microbial habitat stability, which together enhanced the biological control potential with similar findings reported. In earlier studies [36], where it was revealed that biochar-based formulations strengthened microbial activity and pest suppression in maize and vegetable systems.

The field observation also suggested that combining organic and inorganic amendments with biological agents enhances plant vigor and productivity in both pest-managed (sprayed) and untreated (non-sprayed) conditions which substantiated the ecological

benefits of integrating microbial consortia with moderate nutrient inputs. The combined application of NPK (50 kg N ha⁻¹), mycorrhiza (*Glomus intraradices*), biochar, and Bt (T₂) improved growth, chlorophyll content, and yield compared to mineral fertilizer alone. This synergy is attributed to the complementary functions of the components: mycorrhiza enhances phosphorus uptake and stress tolerance [37]; biochar improves nutrient retention and soil structure [38]; and Bt provides pest suppression [39]. The consistent chlorophyll content and reduced foliar damage under both sprayed and non-sprayed conditions underscore the resilience of these bioformulations against environmental fluctuations and pest pressure. [40]. Collectively, these results demonstrate that integrated bioformulations containing *Mycorrhiza*, biochar, and *B. thuringiensis* can effectively reduce fall armyworm-induced foliar injury while maintaining stability across management regimes, which emphasized their potential as sustainable alternatives to conventional fertilizer-dependent pest management systems.

The reduced foliar injury in biochar–mycorrhiza–Bt-treated plants confirms their protective role against *S. frugiperda* feeding. The non-significant treatment × spray regime interaction suggests that entomopathogenic microbial treatments are effective across different pest management intensities. This is crucial for smallholder systems where chemical access and affordability are limited [41]. The PCA results indicated that integrated bioformulations contributed most to variation in growth and yield traits, reinforcing the notion that biologically fortified amendments improve plant physiological and agronomic performance under field stress [42,43]. Hence, the study provides evidence that biochar-based microbial formulations particularly those combining Bt and

mycorrhiza represented an effective and eco-friendly alternative to synthetic insecticides in management of Fall armyworm. Their dual function as biocontrol agents and soil fertility enhancers aligns with current global efforts toward sustainable and climate-resilient maize production. Further long-term and multi-location trials are recommended to assess the consistency of these results and the persistence of microbial populations under diverse agroecological conditions. Integrating these bioformulations with complementary IPM strategies such as resistant varieties, habitat diversification, and judicious pesticide use will help to establish a holistic and sustainable pest management framework for *S. frugiperda* in Africa.

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Author Contributions

Iwebaffa Amos Edet and Oluwafolake Adenike Akinbode conceived and designed the study, supervised the experiments, and prepared the initial manuscript draft.

Oluwafolake Adenike Akinbode and George Oluwadamilare Iwebafa conducted the laboratory and field experiments, collected data, and Iwebaffa Amos Edet contributed to data interpretation.

Clement Gboyega Afolabi performed statistical analysis, assisted in data validation, and critically revised the manuscript.

All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Declarations

Ethical Approval

This study did not involve human participants, vertebrate animals, or endangered species. All experimental procedures followed institutional, national, and international guidelines for the safe handling of microbial cultures and agricultural field research.

Consent to Participate

Not applicable. No human participants were involved in this research.

Consent to Publish

Not applicable. This manuscript does not contain any individual person's data in any form (including images, videos, or personal identifiers).